

Design, Manufacturing, and Experimentation of an Innovative Efficient Energy Harvesting Suspension System

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Abstract: This study presents the design, development, and experimental validation of an energy-harvesting suspension system aimed at improving vehicle energy efficiency and supporting sustainable mobility. The proposed system captures vibration energy from road-induced suspension motion, converts it into mechanical energy stored in a flywheel, and stabilizes alternator speed through a one-way clutch mechanism. A cascade circuit regulates output voltage at different thresholds to enhance energy recovery performance. The system was modeled in MATLAB Simulink and experimentally tested under sinusoidal vibrations with various frequencies. Results demonstrated an average power output of 112.64 W at 5 Hz and ± 10 mm amplitude and resistance value 83.3Ω , with a 68.5% efficiency improvement compared to systems lacking the one-way clutch. These findings confirm the system's potential to extend vehicle range, reduce emissions, and increase energy utilization. Technical challenges encountered during development are discussed, and future directions for performance optimization are proposed.

Keywords: ball-screw mechanism; energy harvesting suspension system; mechanical motion rectifier; regenerative suspension system; super capacitor charging

1. Introduction

To address the growing demand for sustainable transportation, the automotive industry is actively pursuing technologies that enhance energy efficiency without compromising vehicle performance. Conventional suspension systems dissipate vibrational energy as heat via hydraulic dampers, representing a significant energy loss. Regenerative suspension systems (RSS) offer a promising solution by converting this wasted mechanical energy into usable electrical power, aligning with global goals for energy conservation and emission reduction¹.

In hybrid and electric vehicles, the recovered energy can extend battery life by supplementing the motor system, while in conventional vehicles, it can support auxiliary loads and reduce alternator demand. Despite their potential, RSS remain in the early stages of development and face challenges in achieving optimal energy recovery without compromising ride comfort or stability under varying conditions^{2,3}.

This study presents the design, fabrication, and experimental validation of an energy harvesting suspension system. The system captures vibration energy

under varying excitation frequencies and stores it via a self-regulating unit responsive to alternator output, enhancing energy recovery efficiency. Targeting vehicles with internal combustion engines, hybrid and electric vehicles the approach promotes fuel efficiency and emission reduction without affecting suspension performance. The work contributes to the development of regenerative technologies and supports the transition towards more sustainable transportation solutions.

Research efforts have explored various mechanisms for energy harvesting, including electromagnetic, hydraulic-electric, mechanical, and piezoelectric systems. Electromagnetic approaches have received significant attention due to their structural simplicity and ease of retrofitting into conventional suspension architectures⁴⁻⁷. Tang et al achieved an efficiency of up to 78% with a linear electromagnetic damper, although damping performance was limited⁸. Similar systems by Zhang et al⁹. and Gysen et al.¹⁰ integrated rack-and-pinion or active control, yet often faced constraints in damping force or complexity. Advances in system modeling and nonlinear electromagnetic design have further improved bandwidth and energy output^{11,12}.

Hydraulic-electric systems typically offer higher energy recovery potential. Galluzzi et al.¹³⁾ demonstrated a hydraulic damper that converted linear fluctuations into alternator rotation, achieving 41.7% efficiency. Other studies reported outputs exceeding 200W under harmonic excitation, with stable damping characteristics¹⁴⁻¹⁶⁾. Hybrid configurations, such as the hydraulic-electromagnetic shock absorber (HESA) developed for railway bogies, showed effective vibration reduction and energy generation¹⁷⁾. Optimization algorithms, including Hi-PSO, have further enhanced efficiency in such systems¹⁸⁾.

Piezoelectric energy harvesting, though generally limited in power output, offers compact, lightweight designs suitable for low-power electronics¹⁹⁻²²⁾. Recent works have explored combining piezoelectric and electromagnetic elements to increase performance across broader frequency ranges²³⁻²⁵⁾. Furthermore, novel configurations using arc-shaped piezoelectric components embedded in rotating elements have enabled energy harvesting from rotational vibrations. These systems, applied in bearing housings and elastic supports, not only generate power but also offer real-time monitoring for faults - highlighting the growing role of piezoelectric technology.

Mechanical systems, using direct mechanical linkages like ball screws or gear trains, have achieved the highest energy conversion efficiencies²⁶⁻²⁸⁾. These systems are valued for their minimal energy loss and robust structural design. For instance, two-bar linkages and ball screw mechanisms demonstrated consistent output across a range of road frequencies, while efficient gear selection strategies balanced damping and transmission efficiency²⁹⁻³¹⁾.

A variety of hybrid systems have also emerged, blending different mechanisms to optimize performance. These developments reflect the transition toward self-powered systems, aiming to replace conventional battery-based solutions for onboard sensing and monitoring³¹⁻³³⁾.

Although current regenerative shock absorber technologies have demonstrated a significant capacity for harvesting oscillation energy, they still face notable limitations that hinder their ability to fully replace conventional shock absorbers in practical applications.

One of the primary constraints lies in the energy storage strategy, which often relies solely on voltage regulation and direct charging of supercapacitors arranged in parallel or series configurations. This approach typically overlooks the dynamic interaction between the energy harvesting mechanism and the vehicle's suspension mobility, leading to suboptimal integration and performance under real-world operating conditions. Furthermore, existing regenerative absorber systems often struggle with challenges related to structural complexity, mechanical losses, and response adaptability across varying road surfaces and loading conditions. To overcome these limitations, this paper proposes a novel high-performance regenerative suspension system that integrates a dual ball screw mechanism with differentiated mechanical characteristics, strategically arranged one-way clutches, and a self-regulating control circuit. This configuration allows the system to decouple input motion efficiently and stabilize the energy transfer pathway, thereby enhancing energy recovery consistency and reliability. The harvested energy is stored in a supercapacitor and managed via an intelligent logic circuit that autonomously responds to the system's output voltage and load demand. This enables the system to effectively supply electrical power to auxiliary loads in internal combustion engine vehicles or contribute to extending the driving range of electric vehicles.

In summary, RSS represent a critical innovation for sustainable transportation. While each approach has unique trade-offs in efficiency, complexity, and scalability, ongoing advances in materials, modeling, and hybrid integration continue to push the field toward viable real-world deployment.

2. Design of the energy harvesting suspension system

The design energy harvesting system focuses on overcoming the limitations of existing (RSS) by introducing innovative components and configurations in Table 1. The design and main features of the system are illustrated in Figure 1.

Table 1: Structural parameters of the experimental object for the computational model (determined experimentally)

No.	Structural Parameter Name	Symbol	Value	Unit
1	Sprung mass	M	220	kg
2	Elastic element stiffness	K2	25840	N/m
3	Unsprung mass	m	70	kg
4	Tire stiffness	K1	200000	N/m
5	Tire damping coefficient	C1	50	N.s/m
6	Moment of inertia (alternator + flywheel)	J_{eq}	3.7	kg.cm ²
7	Moment of inertia of the lead screw upward shaft	J_{us}	0.19	kg.cm ²
8	Moment of inertia of the lead screw downward shaft	J_{ds}	0.09	kg.cm ²
9	Moment of inertia of the large gear shaft	J_{lg}	0.29	kg.cm ²
10	Moment of inertia of the small gear shaft	J_{sg}	0.0024	kg.cm ²

11	Gear transmission ratio	r_G	2.5	
12	Gearbox acceleration ratio	r_T	1	
13	Lead pitch of the downward shaft	p_d	0.01	m
14	Lead pitch of the upward shaft	p_u	0.02	m

Fig. 1: Visualization of the 3D structure and the working mechanism of the regenerative suspension system

2.1. Dual ball screw mechanism

The developed system incorporates a dual ball screw mechanism, each featuring distinct design parameters such as thread direction and lead pitch. By leveraging the mechanical interplay between ball screws with opposite threading and unequal leads, the system achieves enhanced shock mitigation capability. Importantly, this configuration enables the realization of asymmetric damping forces during compression and rebound phases, aligning well with the nonlinear damping profiles commonly employed in automotive suspension systems. As a result, the proposed design offers improved dynamic response, smoother ride quality, and more effective vibration suppression compared to existing regenerative damper solutions.

2.2. Mechanical motion rectifier (MMR)

The inclusion of strategically arranged one-way clutches ensures that energy is effectively directed and managed within the system. These clutches help in optimizing the energy conversion process by controlling the direction of motion and minimizing energy loss, thereby improving the system's efficiency.

2.3. One-way clutch-based energy rectification

The direction of mechanical energy flow is regulated through the implementation of a Mechanical Motion Rectifier (MMR), which transforms the bidirectional oscillatory input from the suspension system into

unidirectional rotational output. However, the output motion from the MMR inherently follows a half-sine waveform, resulting in torque fluctuations during energy transmission. To address this issue, a one-way clutch is introduced between the MMR output shaft and the flywheel – alternator assembly. This mechanism enables the continuous high-speed rotation of the flywheel and alternator rotor, decoupling them from the oscillatory input of the MMR's half-sine cycle, the flywheel maintains independent motion, thanks to its inertial energy and the one-way clutch. This configuration ensures smoother alternator operation and effectively mitigates fluctuations in output power caused by the oscillatory dynamics of the suspension system.

2.4. Adjustable circuit for charging super capacitors

Supercapacitors typically require voltage regulation during charging, which results in the upper portion of transient waveforms being clipped - causing considerable energy loss. Additionally, once fully charged, excess generated energy cannot be stored, leading to further inefficiencies. To overcome these challenges, a multi-tiered energy harvesting strategy is introduced, where electrical energy is dynamically routed to three capacitor banks based on voltage thresholds. Importantly, this routing is managed by an automatic control logic rather than parallel charging, ensuring that each bank receives energy according to its

designated voltage range (high, medium, or low). This architecture enhances energy recovery and system efficiency by reducing overvoltage clipping and storage saturation losses, diagram control logic charging capacitor/ super capacitor in Figure 2.

Fig. 2: Voltage storage circuit diagram

3. Modeling regenerative suspension system

3.1. Modeling approach

The dynamic behavior of the regenerative suspension system was modeled using MATLAB Simulink. The model captures vibrational energy from the vehicle suspension motion and converts it into electrical energy through an integrated energy harvesting mechanism. Applying the two-mass (two-degree-of-freedom) oscillation model as illustrated in Figure 3a, the thesis uses the D’alembert principle to establish a differential analysis system and construct mathematical methods to describe the dynamics of this dynamic system. The power and reaction system can be realized in Figure 3b, with the description line described by the displacement q_0 , the displacement of the unsprung mass is Z_1 , and the displacement of the sprung mass is Z_2 ³⁴. The masses M and m oscillating in the Z direction are the inertial force components of the system, respectively $M \cdot \ddot{Z}_2$ and $m \cdot \ddot{Z}_1$.

Fig. 3: Second-order (two-mass) system dynamics model.

The elastic forces and damping forces acting between the sprung mass & the unsprung mass are expressed by:

$$\begin{cases} -M \cdot \frac{d^2 Z_2}{dt^2} - FC_2 - FK_2 = 0 \\ -m \cdot \frac{d^2 Z_1}{dt^2} + FC_2 + FK_2 - FC_1 - FK_1 = 0 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Where: $FK_1 = K_1 \cdot Z_{1td}$; $FC_1 = C_1 \cdot \frac{dZ_{1td}}{dt}$

$$FK_2 = K_2 \cdot Z_{2td}; FC_2 = J_{td} \cdot \frac{d^2 Z_{2td}}{dt^2} + c_{td} \cdot \frac{dZ_{2td}}{dt}$$

$$Z_{2td} = Z_2 - Z_1; Z_{1td} = Z_1 - q_0$$

After substituting the variables, we have the differential system:

$$\begin{cases} \left(- (M + J_{td}) \cdot \frac{d^2 Z_2}{dt^2} + J_{td} \cdot \frac{d^2 Z_1}{dt^2} \right. \\ \quad \left. - c_{td} \cdot \frac{dZ_2}{dt} + c_{td} \cdot \frac{dZ_1}{dt} \right. \\ \quad \left. - K_2 \cdot Z_2 + K_2 \cdot Z_1 = 0 \right) \\ \left(J_{td} \cdot \frac{d^2 Z_2}{dt^2} - (m + J_{td}) \cdot \frac{d^2 Z_1}{dt^2} \right. \\ \quad \left. + c_{td} \cdot \frac{dZ_2}{dt} - (c_{td} + C_1) \cdot \frac{dZ_1}{dt} + K_2 \cdot Z_2 \right. \\ \quad \left. - (K_2 + K_1) \cdot Z_1 + K_1 \cdot q_0 + C_1 \cdot \frac{dq_0}{dt} = 0 \right) \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Where: The term J_{td} represents the equivalent moment of inertia, summing all individual inertias across different operational stages. Similarly, c_{td} accounts for total damping, combining both mechanical and electrical effects and the component parameters are detailed in Table 1.

The differential equation describes the dynamic interaction between the two degrees of freedom by linking position, velocity, and acceleration under internal and external forces. Solving it enables prediction of system behavior and estimation of the alternator’s rotational speed via the screw shaft’s velocity relation. A key enhancement is the adaptive damping mechanism, which varies with the relative velocity between sprung and unsprung masses and incorporates tire damping, offering improved accuracy under changing road conditions.

3.2. Computational dynamics model analysis

The complex nonlinear model between the elements in the regenerative damping is formed with the use of a mechanical rectifier, through a reasonably arranged one way clutch the alternator is allowed to engage and disengage from the oscillation source without being limited by the movement of the suspension system. In the schematic diagram presented in Figure 4, when the element m translates, in the engaged state we have the electric damping coefficient c_e and the inertia of the alternator J_G .

Fig. 4: Dynamic diagram of the system in the meshed state

The alternator operates in connection with the oscillating source thanks to the characteristic of the clutch after the mechanical rectifier, which can be obtained by the proposed regeneration method according to:

$$T_c = \left(\begin{array}{l} J_{us} \cdot r_g \cdot r_T + J_{ds} \cdot r_g \cdot r_T \\ + 2 \cdot J_{lg} \cdot r_g \cdot r_T + J_{sg} \cdot r_T + J_G \end{array} \right) \cdot \frac{d^2 \varphi_G}{dt^2} + c_e \cdot \frac{d\varphi_G}{dt} + c_m \cdot \frac{d\varphi_G}{dt} \quad (3)$$

Since the oscillation source is represented by a sinusoidal function, when the input velocity reaches its maximum amplitude and changes direction of motion, at t_1 , the torque acting on the alternator drops to 0.

Fig. 5: Dynamic diagram of the system in the disengaged state

At that time, the external one way clutch of the rectifier will disconnect the alternator from the oscillation source, preventing torque/power from being transmitted between them, preventing their velocity from being pulled to 0 by the oscillation source in Figure.5.

$$T_u = \left(\begin{array}{l} J_{us} \cdot r_g \cdot r_T + J_{ds} \cdot r_g \cdot r_T \\ + 2 \cdot J_{lg} \cdot r_g \cdot r_T + J_{sg} \cdot r_T \end{array} \right) \cdot \frac{d^2 \varphi_{input}}{dt^2} + c_m \cdot \frac{d\varphi_{input}}{dt} \quad (4)$$

Where: $\frac{d\varphi_{input}}{dt}$ is angular speed of rectifier output.

According to Newton's second law, when the clutch is released, the rotor will rotate freely due to its own momentum without receiving any torque from the input vibration. Assuming no air friction during the torque transmission, the torque T_g acting from the vibration source to the alternator and the electric load is described by the following differential equation:

$$T_g = J_G \cdot \frac{d^2 \varphi}{dt^2} + c_e \cdot \frac{d\varphi}{dt} = 0 \quad (5)$$

Based on the system parameters, the time t_1 is determined as the time when the oscillating source starts to stop transmitting energy to the alternator, corresponding to half of the oscillation period, and can be represented by the formula:

$$t_1 = \frac{1}{\omega} \arctan \left(\frac{c_e}{\omega \cdot J_G} \right) + \frac{k\pi}{\omega}, k = 0,1,2,3 \dots \quad (6)$$

During the process from t_1 to t_2 , the angular velocity of the alternator will gradually decrease according to the exponential law³⁵, reflecting the natural damping property of the oscillation.

$$\varphi = A \cdot e^{\lambda \cdot (t-t_1)} \quad (7)$$

In the above equation, λ is called the damping factor, which determines how much the system slows down over time. Based on the angular position derivative to determine the speed, the alternator rotational speed during the disconnection period can be calculated based on the exponential function expression, reflecting the speed decay over time:

$$\frac{d\varphi_G}{dt} = - \frac{d\varphi_{input}(t_1)}{dt} \cdot e^{-\frac{c_e}{J_G}(t-t_1)}, t_1 \leq t \leq t_2 \quad (8)$$

The instantaneous re-connection time t_2 can be solved numerically from $d\varphi_G/dt$ for each t_1 with different k . That is, when the system is excited by a certain velocity input, the full-cycle rotational speed of the alternator can be determined by the following:

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{d\varphi_G}{dt}(t) = \frac{d\varphi_{input}(t)}{dt}, t_2 \leq t \leq t_1 + \frac{\pi}{\omega} \\ \frac{d\varphi_G}{dt}(t) = - \left(\frac{d\varphi_{input}(t)}{dt} \right) \cdot e^{-\frac{c_e}{J_G}(t-t_1)}, t_1 \leq t \leq t_2 \end{array} \quad (9)$$

The continuity condition requires that the angular velocity must be satisfied at time t_2 , the angular velocity of the alternator before and after reconnection to the system must be equal. This ensures the continuity of the system when transitioning between connected and disconnected states. The continuity condition equation is:

$$\cos(\omega t_1) + \cos(\omega t_2) e^{\frac{c_e}{J_G}(t-t_1)} = 0, t_1 \leq t_2 \leq t_1 + \omega\pi. \quad (10)$$

Instead of describing the total input power separately, the simulation results show the amount of power that can be transferred by means of reactive power. The reactive power from the oscillating source during the connection phase can be expressed by the following formula:

$$P_{c-r} = \left(\begin{array}{c} (J_{us} \cdot r_g \cdot r_T + J_{ds} \cdot r_g \cdot r_T) \cdot \frac{d^2 \varphi_{input}}{dt^2} \\ + 2 \cdot J_{lg} \cdot r_g \cdot r_T + J_{sg} \cdot r_T + J_G \\ + (c_e + c_m) \cdot \frac{d\varphi_{input}}{dt} \end{array} \right) \cdot \frac{d\varphi_{input}}{dt} \quad (11)$$

While the reactive power during the disconnection phase

3.3. The analysis of numerical results

To determine the value of regenerative voltage in the system, it is necessary to rely on the operating principles of a 3-phase alternator as well as relevant research materials that have been reviewed. However, due to

when there is no inertia of the alternator is expressed as:

$$P_{u-r} = \left(\begin{array}{c} (J_{us} \cdot r_g \cdot r_T + J_{ds} \cdot r_g \cdot r_T) \cdot \frac{d^2 \varphi_{input}}{dt^2} \\ + c_m \cdot \frac{d\varphi_{input}}{dt} \end{array} \right) \cdot \frac{d\varphi_{input}}{dt} \quad (12)$$

insufficient information and the inability to fully identify the specific technical parameters of the alternator used, an experimental method has been applied to determine the output voltage value based on the rotational speed of the alternator in Figure 6.

Fig. 6: Block diagram for modeling of new RSA

Under a step input of 0.05 m at 0.3 s (Figure 7), the system exhibits damped oscillatory behavior. The wheel displacement Z1 responds rapidly with higher amplitude, while the body displacement Z2 stabilizes more slowly. The minor phase lag of Z1 relative to the input reflects tire and suspension flexibility.

Fig. 7: Response of proposed RSA

The decaying response between 0.4 s and 0.8 s confirms effective damping, indicating the system’s capacity to absorb shocks and maintain ride comfort. The energy recovery performance was compared between the nonlinear system with and without a mechanical rectifier. Under a sinusoidal input signal with a frequency of 3.125Hz ±10 mm as shown in Figure.8, the mechanical rectifier enabled continuous alternator operation, preventing the output power from dropping to zero.

Fig. 8: The results under a sinusoidal input signal with a frequency of 3.125 Hz, amplitude of 10 mm

This resulted in a 66.9865% increase in average recovered energy, demonstrating the one way clutch after rectifier’s effectiveness in optimizing energy harvesting. Overall, the simulation and modeling efforts reveal that the proposed regenerative suspension system, with its advanced damping mechanism and mechanical rectifier, significantly enhances energy recovery and system performance. This approach ensures more consistent alternator operation, greater energy recovery potential, and improved ride comfort and stability.

4. Result and analysis

To comprehensively evaluate the performance of the energy harvesting system over different excitation frequency ranges, the test is an average of 5 measurements below is the experimental layout diagram show as in

Figure 9.

Fig. 9: Schematic diagram of regenerative damping system testing setup

4.1. Validation of theoretical model through experimental analysis

To validate the accuracy of the theoretical model, an experimental approach was employed to assess the correlation between theoretical predictions and

experimental results. The experimental setup was designed at a full 1:1 scale, reflecting the actual dimensions and specifications of the physical vehicle system. This approach ensures geometric consistency and alignment of key parameters between the theoretical model and the experimental system.

Correlation analysis (correlation coefficient $r=0,978195$)

Fig. 10: Graph of correlation between modeling and experiment at harmonic sine in conditions: $f = 3.125$ Hz, ± 10 mm and resistance value 83.3Ω

The vehicle's specifications were integrated into the theoretical model to ensure dimensional consistency. Under a 3.125 Hz excitation with ± 10 mm amplitude, a strong correlation ($R = 0.9782$) was observed between theoretical ($Z2lt$) and experimental ($Z2tt$) results. The

regenerative voltage (82 – 92 V) aligned closely with model predictions in Figure.10. These outcomes validate the model's accuracy and reliability, confirming its suitability for predicting system behavior and guiding future design optimization. Experiments were also

conducted across various frequency ranges, leading to several new findings, which are summarized in Table 2 and illustrated in Figure 11.

Table 2: Average experimental results under different conditions

Stimulation frequency (Hz)	Alternator speed (RPM)	Current max (Ampere)	Regeneration voltage (Volt)	Power electrical(W)
2.05	600	0.056	31.6 – 45.1	1.77 – 2.53
2.3	824	0.1225	39 – 51.5	4.78 – 6.31
2.6	1068	0.178	56 – 68	9.96 – 12.104
3.125	1507	0.2695	82 – 92	28.66 – 32.15
4	2397	0.5865	122.3	71.716
4.7	2616	0.607	148	87.836
5	3060	0.6665	169	112.638

4.2. Experiment and change the stimulation frequency

Fig 11d illustrates that the displacement of the vehicle body is significantly lower than that of the road surface, indicating that the RSS effectively attenuates vibrations, contributing to ride comfort and dynamic stability. Notably, at frequencies above 4 Hz, a downward shift in the mean body position was observed, suggesting a lower center of

gravity that potentially improves high - speed stability. The phase lag between the sprung mass and the excitation signal implies partial energy dissipation and conversion into electrical energy. At 102 Hz, the system achieves peak output of 169 V and 0.6665 A in Table 2, demonstrating effective energy harvesting under high-frequency conditions.

(a) Displacement response of the body element and alternator power response at 2.05Hz, amplitude ± 10 mm and resistance 83.3Ω

(b) Displacement response of the body element and alternator power response at 3.125Hz, amplitude ± 10 mm and resistance 83.3Ω

(c) Displacement response of the body element and alternator power response at 4 Hz, amplitude ± 10 mm and resistance 83.3Ω

(d) Displacement response of the body element and alternator power response at 5 Hz, amplitude ± 10 mm and resistance 83.3Ω
Fig. 11: Displacement response of body element and alternator power response at different appropriate frequencies

Fig. 12: Amplitude-frequency characteristics of RSS

Simulation results complement experimental data by extending the frequency analysis beyond physical test limits. At low excitation frequencies, body displacement is high while power generation remains low. In the mid-frequency range (5 - 6.5 Hz), displacement decreases significantly, and regenerative power peaks -highlighting this as the optimal operating zone for both vibration isolation and energy recovery as shown in Figure.12. At higher frequencies, both vibration attenuation and energy output decline due to limitations in damping response and potential wheel lift-off, which may compromise safety and performance.

5. Conclusion

5.1. Experimental results and analysis

The experimental and simulation results demonstrate a clear relationship between excitation frequency and system performance. The vehicle body exhibits maximum displacement within the resonance range of 2.05 - 3.125 Hz, indicating strong suspension response in this region. However, the highest regenerative voltage was observed at 5 Hz, outside the resonance band, suggesting that optimal energy harvesting occurs at higher frequencies. Simulink simulations further confirm that the most efficient energy recovery lies within the 5 – 6.5 Hz range. This indicates that energy harvesting efficiency can be enhanced without compromising ride comfort by targeting operation outside the resonance zone. By converting vibrational energy into usable electricity, the system contributes not only to energy efficiency but also to sustainable vehicle operation.

5.2. Challenges and Future Directions

Although the prototype demonstrated promising results, several challenges remain. Limited testing time and non-optimized structural design may have affected the accuracy and generalizability of the results. Future work should focus on multi-objective optimization to simultaneously improve vibration isolation and energy harvesting. Integrating adaptive control of flywheel inertia and advanced power electronics for rectification could further enhance energy recovery. Extending the system to various vehicle types with different dynamic requirements would broaden its applicability and reinforce its role in advancing sustainable and energy-aware transportation systems.

References

- 1) N. White, S. Beeby, "Energy harvesting for autonomous systems," Artech House, 2010.
https://books.google.com.vn/books?hl=vi&lr=&id=7H9xdFd4sikC&oi=fnd&pg=PR5&dq=Energy+harvesting+for+autonomous+systems,%E2%80%9D+Artech+House,+2010&ots=2PS48FbTJL&sig=Ye3j8wRZI0m9MmXj7h8e0kzGLR8&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q=Energy%20harvesting%20for%20autonomous%20systems%2C%E2%80%9D%20Artech%20House%2C%202010&f=false
- 2) H. Pan, L. Qi, Z. Zhang, J. Yan, "Kinetic energy harvesting technologies for applications in land transportation: A comprehensive review," *Applied Energy*, 286 (2021).
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2021.116518>.
- 3) M.A.A. Abdelkareem, L. Xu, M.K.A. Ali, A. Elagouz, J. Mi, S. Guo, Y. Liu, L. Zuo, "Vibration energy harvesting in automotive suspension system: A detailed review," *Applied energy*, 229 672-699 (2018).
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2018.08.030>
- 4) C. Wei, X. Jing, "A comprehensive review on vibration energy harvesting: Modelling and realization," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 74 1-18 (2017).
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2017.01.073>
- 5) X. Wang, Q. Wang, W. Wang, Y. Cui, Y. Song,

- “Performance investigation of piezoelectric-mechanical electromagnetic compound vibration energy harvester for electric tractor,” *Energy*, 281 (2023).
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2023.128285>
- 6) S. Bai, C. Liu, “Overview of energy harvesting and emission reduction technologies in hybrid electric vehicles,” *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 147 (2021).
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2021.111188>
 - 7) Y. Tan, Y. Dong, X. Wang, “Review of MEMS electromagnetic vibration energy harvester,” *Journal of Microelectromechanical Systems*, 26 (1) 1-16 (2016). DOI: 10.1109/JMEMS.2016.2611677
 - 8) X. Tang, T. Lin, L. Zuo, “Design and optimization of a tubular linear electromagnetic vibration energy harvester,” *IEEE/ASME Transactions On Mechatronics*, 19 (2) 615-622 (2013). DOI: 10.1109/TMECH.2013.2249666
 - 9) R. Zhang, X. Wang, Z. Liu, “A novel regenerative shock absorber with a speed doubling mechanism and its Monte Carlo simulation,” *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, 417 260-276 (2018).
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsv.2017.12.017>
 - 10) B.L.J. Gysen, T.P.J. van der Sande, J.J.H. Paulides, E.A. Lomonova, “Efficiency of a regenerative direct-drive electromagnetic active suspension,” *IEEE transactions on vehicular technology*, 60 (4) 1384-1393 (2011). DOI: 10.1109/TVT.2011.2131160
 - 11) S. Zhu, W. Shen, Y. Xu, “Linear electromagnetic devices for vibration damping and energy harvesting: Modeling and testing,” *Engineering Structures*, 34 198-212 (2012).
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2011.09.024>
 - 12) T. Yang, S. Zhou, S. Fang, W. Qin, D.J. Inman “Nonlinear vibration energy harvesting and vibration suppression technologies: Designs, analysis, and applications,” *Applied Physics Reviews*, 8 (3) (2021).
<https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0051432>
 - 13) R. Galluzzi, Y. Xu, N. Amati, A. Tonoli, “Optimized design and characterization of motor-pump unit for energy-regenerative shock absorbers,” *Applied Energy*, 210 16-27 (2018).
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2017.10.100>
 - 14) K.A. Cunefare, E.A. Skow, A. Erturk, J. Savor, N. Verma, M.R. Cacan “Energy harvesting from hydraulic pressure fluctuations,” *Smart Materials and Structures* 22 (2) (2013). DOI 10.1088/0964-1726/22/2/025036
 - 15) C. Li, R. Zhu, M. Liang, S. Yang, “Integration of shock absorption and energy harvesting using a hydraulic rectifier,” *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, 333 (17) 3904-3916 (2014).
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsv.2014.04.020>
 - 16) Y. Zhang, H. Chen, K. Guo, X. Zhang, S.E. Li, “Electro-hydraulic damper for energy harvesting suspension: Modeling, prototyping and experimental validation,” *Applied energy*, 199, 1-12 (2017).
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2017.04.085>
 - 17) J. Mi, L. Xu, S. Guo, L. Meng, M.A.A. Abdelkareem, “Energy harvesting potential comparison study of a novel railway vehicle bogie system with the hydraulic-electromagnetic energy-regenerative shock absorber” In *ASME/IEEE Joint Rail Conference, American Society of Mechanical Engineers: 50718 V001T007A004* (2017).
<https://doi.org/10.1115/JRC2017-2241>
 - 18) Q. Zhou, S. Guo, L. Xu, X. Guo, H. Williams, H. Xu, F. Yan, “Global optimization of the hydraulic-electromagnetic energy-harvesting shock absorber for road vehicles with human-knowledge-integrated particle swarm optimization scheme,” *IEEE/ASME Transactions on Mechatronics*, 26 (3) 1225-1235 (2021). DOI: 10.1109/TMECH.2021.3055815
 - 19) B. Lafarge, C. Delebarre, S. Grondel, O. Curea, A. Hacala, “Analysis and optimization of a piezoelectric harvester on a car damper” *Physics Procedia*, 70 970-973 (2015).
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phpro.2015.08.202>
 - 20) M. Safaei, H.A. Sodano, S.R. Anton, “A review of energy harvesting using piezoelectric materials: state-of-the-art a decade later (2008–2018),” *Smart materials and structures*, 28 (11) (2019). DOI 10.1088/1361-665X/ab36e4
 - 21) Z. Zhao, T. Wang, B. Zhang, J. Shi, “Energy harvesting from vehicle suspension system by piezoelectric harvester” *Mathematical Problems in Engineering*, 2019 (1) (2019).
<https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/1086983>
 - 22) R. Tavares, M. Ruderman, “Energy harvesting using piezoelectric transducers for suspension systems,” *Mechatronics*, 65, 102294 (2020).
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mechatronics.2019.102294>
 - 23) S. Alhumaid, D. Hess, R. Guldiken, “Energy regeneration from vehicle unidirectional suspension system by a non-contact piezo-magneto harvester,” *Engineering Research Express*, 3 (1) (2021). DOI 10.1088/2631-8695/abea28
 - 24) M. Wang, Y. Xia, H. Pu, Y. Sun, J. Ding, J. Luo, S. Xie, Y. Peng, Q. Zhang, Z. Li, “Piezoelectric energy harvesting from suspension structures with piezoelectric layers,” *Sensors*, 20 (13) (2020).
<https://doi.org/10.3390/s20133755>
 - 25) X. Shan, S. Guan, Z. Liu, Z. Xu, T. Xie, “A new energy harvester using a piezoelectric and suspension electromagnetic mechanism,” *Journal of Zhejiang University SCIENCE A*, 14 (12) 890-897 (2013).
[doi:10.1631/jzus.A1300210](https://doi.org/10.1631/jzus.A1300210)
 - 26) L. Qi, J. Song, Y. Wang, M. Yi, Z. Zhang, J. Yan, “Mechanical motion rectification-based

- electromagnetic vibration energy harvesting technology: A review” *Energy*, 289 (130030) (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2023.130030>
- 27) L.E. Bowen, “Estudio teórico-experimental de sistemas de recuperación de energía en la suspensión,” Universidad Antonio de Nebrija, 566389 (2018). <https://dialnet.unirioja.es/servlet/tesis?codigo=285740>
- 28) L. Xie, J. Li, X. Li, L. Huang, S. Cai, “Damping-tunable energy-harvesting vehicle damper with multiple controlled generators: design, modeling and experiments,” *Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing*, 99 859-872 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ymsp.2017.07.005>
- 29) Y.M. Roshan, A. Maravandi, M. Moallem, “Power electronics control of an energy regenerative mechatronic damper,” *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, 62 (5) 3052-3060 (2015).
- 30) Z. Zhang, X. Zhang, W. Chen, Y. Rasim, W. Salman, H. Pan, Y. Yuan, C. Wang, “A high-efficiency energy regenerative shock absorber using supercapacitors for renewable energy applications in range extended electric vehicle,” *Applied Energy*, 178 177-188 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2016.06.054>
- 31) M.R. Hajidavalloo, J. Cosner, Z. Li, W.C. Tai, Z. Song, “Simultaneous suspension control and energy harvesting through novel design and control of a new nonlinear energy harvesting shock absorber” *IEEE transactions on vehicular technology*, 71 (6) 6073-6087 (2022).
- 32) L. Zhang, F. Zhang, Z. Qin, Q. Han, T. Wang, F. Chu, “Piezoelectric energy harvester for rolling bearings with capability of self-powered condition monitoring,” *Energy*, 238 121770 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2021.121770>
- 33) L. Qin, L. Zhang, J. Feng, F. Zhang, Q. Han, Z. Qin, F. Chu, “A hybrid triboelectric-piezoelectric smart squirrel cage with self-sensing and self-powering capabilities” *Nano Energy*, 124 109506 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nanoen.2024.109506>
- 34) D. Hanafi, M.F. Zakaria, R. Omar, M.N.M. Than, M.F. Rahmat, R. Ghazali, “Neuro Model Approach for a Quarter Car Passive Suspension Systems,” *Applied Mechanics and Materials*, 775 103-109 (2015). DOI:10.4028/www.scientific.net/AMM.775.103
- 35) J.L. Safko, H. Goldstein, C. Poole, “Classical Mechanics,” Chapter Oscillations, 2015. https://d1wqtxts1xzle7.cloudfront.net/57055992/Goldstein-libre.pdf?1532365194=&response-content-disposition=inline%3B+filename%3DGoldstein.pdf&Expires=1750966405&Signature=RfszMXwKFzeo7umLncbqsu7pbjCIG0svcWR~LAvYlex1jeB1Q-SShyq1Kl~S~uW7rpV5zON6kSKGRIqNqymSCuCAVpvG0TJw0AkLZxH~hmfq~nz-CSw3i160SbByISIIzIkvoY28HIWcatrGWB4mOgfB~YTkqzSsiq-nMjqZ3x-npoMW4kqx0J7agI8ib6u8cz2gdxxN1dtorAtQzyPRFBPFxxbtuKgstprWoPJOS5SGjxYmIiFEY~brICBPFv4kFcod32BNzs8-M5oddgqRv4dof3PzsUvjNGa8AOu5zrQQDpJebrV0Qj9UdS2GhOKYVnQgd6e-V4FAyu6j4i3iw__&Key-Pair-Id=APKAJLOHF5GGSLRBV4ZA